

English Language Teaching through YouTube: A Study on Bangladeshi YouTube Channels

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***Abstract:** The study attempts to explore the present scenario of YouTube language teaching in Bangladesh and to define how the YouTubers select material and conduct classes on YouTube. This study explored ten renowned YouTube language channels in terms of some variables like video characteristics, attractiveness, clarity, reaction, content, skills and teaching methodology. For this purpose, a questionnaire survey is conducted and naturalistic observation is carried out. In addition, a Focus Group Discussion (FGD) was made to get learners' opinions. The findings show that except three channels most of them are following the traditional approach of language teaching. The findings also indicate that most of the facilitators belong to nonlinguistic background and do not have any teacher training experience. Again, inadequate focus is given in developing individual language skills. Therefore, the YouTube language teaching needs modification.*

***Keywords:** Netnography, language teaching, teaching method, effectiveness of teaching*

1. Introduction

Challenging contexts in language classroom and increasing online communication through YouTube lead towards answering the question to what extent this media of communication has been utilized in teaching language skills among Bangladeshi learners. To begin with, the problems of language classroom include lack of potential materials to meet multiple learning styles in one classroom, learners' autonomy to choose individual stimulating lessons and adequate time to focus on individual psychology and personality to ensure motivated learning. In this regard, YouTube can be an

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effective instrument to make a connection between satisfying the particular educational requirements of the language learners and responding to the needs of foreign language education (Terantino, 2011). According to Balbay and Kilis (2017), learners can be benefited to a large extent from the videos in the learning language playlist on YouTube channels. There are several YouTube channels operated by native ELT practitioners like EngVid, Speak English with Mr. Duncan, Learn English with English Class 101.com, Real English, BBC Learning English etc. teaching English to both the native and non-native language learners in order to develop the linguistic knowledge of English language. Following the idea, Bangladeshi YouTubers have already introduced different English language learning channels, among which '10 Minutes School', 'Tutorial World 20', 'Talent Hunt Institute', 'Saifur's Education' and 'Indigenous Multimedia', 'Unique English World' etc. are prominent ones.

Since a YouTube channel can be operated by anyone and it has become an earning source for the young people of Bangladesh, the language teaching channels, specially the most popular ones, should be investigated in terms of quality of materials provided, expertise of the teachers and methods of pedagogy to ensure positive backwash effect in authentic context.

2. Background of the Study

Learning English incorporating technology has begun to flourish in Bangladesh at every corner of the country. Now the prevailing computer mediated communication through different social Medias is playing a pivotal role in bringing significant changes in the language of communication throughout the world and the language controlling authorities warmly welcome these changes. YouTube founded by Steve Chen, Chad Hurley and Jawed Karim in February, 2005 is an open two-fold social media where people can upload their videos and let other watch and post their opinions by putting comments below the video (Jones & Cuthrell, 2011). In Bangladesh, due to easy access to the internet, the L2 learners are frequently using YouTube and other new media tools with a view to enhancing their skills in English (Hasan, Hossain, Bhuiyan & Mahmud, 2016). It is also a scope for the people, who want to be a teacher, to show their expertise and teaching skills by producing and posting videos. In Bangladesh, more than 20 English language teaching channels teach the language and among them only one channel named 10 Minutes

School got the official recognition from YouTube. Rests of them are teaching English without recognition but the number of the viewers and subscribers of those channels are adequate enough to get them official. When these channels upload language related videos, the subscribers watch those videos and post their comments on the comment bar about any topic with which they face problems.

On the other hand, no language teaching authority has yet evaluated the teaching content, target learners group, teaching methodology, teaching experience etc. of those channels. Among them, some channels use animation, bold-text, box-note, graphic explanation that help different kinds of learners to comprehend the lesson. Some of the channels just provide the video and the linguistic content but no facilitator come in front of the camera. Some uses animation whereas rests are just slide-oriented lecture on grammatical items on language. Most of the channels focus on the grammatical items, which are important for the board exam such as SSC, HSC etc. and necessary for any competitive exam in Bangladesh. Here figure 1 is taken from 10 Minutes School where a facilitator is conducting a class on tense and its aspect and different linguistic contents are visible which have already been conducted. Here we can see the lesson on tense and its different aspects of tense and the method of teaching is completely traditional like Grammar Translation Method. The lower part is showing the lesson on different components of grammar like preposition, parts of speech, pronoun etc. In addition, the class conductor gives feedback on the comments section in written format or presents another class on the problematic issues of the running class.

Figure 1: Homepage of 10 minutes school

The popularity of online language teaching in Bangladesh has spread so rapidly that it is needed to be examined to find out the effectiveness and outcome of this type of language teaching and learning. This type of study has not been done in Bangladesh before. In this regard, this research attempts to explore the current scenario of Bangladeshi YouTube language teaching practice particularly English language teaching.

3. The Rationale of the Study

The intention for choosing this study is the remarkable use of the YouTube website, its free-of-charge availability, and ease of use. Thus, many language tutors can use the website's videos to teach English. Many students around the world are watching language learning tutorials, and many clips have been viewed millions of times (Snelson, 2008). Another reason is the negative concerns that learners face when studying in the traditional way. As an illustration, teaching English courses might be complex, and learners need a method to simplify the lessons to understand them better. Moreover, pupils may feel uninterested in the class since there is no enjoyment. Additionally, pupils are likely to face difficulty with lecturing or teaching that follows the traditional teaching routine; they may prefer another mode of learning English. However, by using YouTube videos, students can gain a considerable number of advantages and motivations that make the learning process active. In addition, it may offer teachers a chance to overcome a number of negative

concerns and involve learners in a new method of teaching. Furthermore, it can be a helpful tool for tutors to use in their lessons. In this regard, no research work can be found which investigates the use and utility of YouTube videos teaching English language in Bangladeshi context. According to Terantino (2011), there is a paucity of research about the influence of YouTube videos on English language learning and little experiential investigation to elucidate effective ways to incorporate Web-based applications into overseas language instruction. In addition, language teachers may not have enough background or knowledge of the positive impact of YouTube videos for teaching purposes.

4. Research Question

The study seeks to investigate the following research questions:

1. How are YouTube language classes conducted in Bangladesh?
2. How do YouTube language facilitators select content and material, and sequence them to upload on the channel?
3. How much time do learners spend on the YouTube class and how do they overcome any difficulty while facing problems in the lesson?

5. Significance of the Study

The study will provide an in depth knowledge of YouTube language teaching and learning in Bangladesh. The English language learners of Bangladesh will be able to know the current situation of online language teaching and its effectiveness. They will be able to find out the best YouTube language teaching channels to subscribe and watch their videos for their language development. On the other hand, it will suggest them to watch those channels, which have a good amount of input and covered almost all four skills, i.e. listening, reading, speaking and writing of English language. Besides, the current ELT practitioners of our country will know the essence of very recent growing phenomenon of YouTube language teaching in Bangladesh. The findings of this study can be used as a reference for any future research on the same arena.

6. Literature Review

YouTube is a very attractive social medium that contributes to the global

education (Bonk, 2009). Duffy (2008) remarks that the educators teaching English language through YouTube are increasing rapidly. In addition, YouTube offers fast and fun access to language and culture-based videos and instruction from all over the globe (Terantino, 2011, p. 11). In other words, YouTube is making new demands on learning that are changing the learning ecology (Kwan et al., 2008).

Using YouTube in education has a positive influence on the learning and teaching process, particularly in classes (Rice et al. 2011). On the other hand, Wu et al. (2002) examined the effective use of videos on the internet and recommended several directions and approaches that stressed the effectiveness of using video in education. According to a study by Boster et al. (2006), videos may influence educational achievement in a positive way. Many researchers have tried to shed light on the vital role of YouTube videos for teaching and learning in the classroom. In another study, Berk (2009) emphasized the key role of teaching language in the college classroom by using YouTube videos. He mentioned 15 benefits regarding why videos should be used in language teaching. Seilstad (2012) investigated using YouTube clips as a new method for teaching English language students in Morocco.

7. Research Methodology

7.1 Netnographic Research

In an easy definition, netnography, coined by Kozinets, is the study of any online community to understand their behavior. According to Kozinets (1988), it is a type of online ethnography which provides “guidelines for the adaptation of participant-observation procedures to the contingencies of online community” which manifest through computer-mediated communications. There are a few features which separate netnography from ethnography such as research focus, communication focus, research method, data collection, number of participants etc. Though it is different from ethnography, to some extent both have similarity. Netnography is naturalistic, immersive, descriptive and multi-method research like ethnography. As Netnography uses authentic data and conducts observation without intruding online users, it is considered as more realistic than other approaches such as interviews, focus groups, surveys and experiments (Kozinets, 2015).

7.2 Design and framework

It is a mixed-method approach research where a questionnaire was used to collect quantitative data and naturalistic observation, interviews and focused group discussion were used to gather the descriptive data. To observe the channels, some variables like video characteristic, clarity, attractiveness, contents, skills, and teaching philosophy are taken into consideration. On the other hand, some other aspects related to language teaching and learning are emphasized while observing the YouTube videos.

7.3 Sample

The sample of this study was selected based on the subscriber, viewer and comments giver of the different YouTube language learning videos. Though YouTube language teaching is emerging in Bangladesh, there are more than twenty-five channels on language teaching. The channels havenot been chosen randomly rather these channels are the most viewed and subscribed by Bangladeshi students. On the other side, the selective hundred and fifty language learners who are regularly posting comments on these channels are selected for the questionnaire and the respective teachers of these channels are selected for interviews.

7.4 Data Collection

Data has been collected randomly from hundred and fifty language learners who watch different YouTube channels to learn language and interact through comments. Before selecting them, the researchers did a piloting on their participation on the channel's activity and observed their comments on the comments box like which language they are using to comment, e.g. Bangla, English or phonetic Bangla (representation of Bangla by English alphabet). In addition, 10 selected YouTube channels were observed and their respective operators were interviewed. Data collection tools were observations, qualitative question, focus group discussion etc. In observation, the investigators observed the language learning videos created by these channels in terms of duration, audio quality, video quality, teaching style, teaching philosophy, teacher's background, teaching atmosphere, number of subscribers, number of viewers, effective comments, background music, using language (both or only one language), repetition, recap (reminder of

previous class), webpage outlook, using animation while teaching, using real life examples and teaching method. In addition, several socio cultural and socio economic issues which were related to language teaching and learning were taken into consideration. For the qualitative part, some channel coordinators and class conductors were interviewed and their valuable answers and remarks facilitated the researchers to write down the answer in detail. On the other hand, focus group discussion was done through creating a group on 'hangouts' a social communication site, which is a part of Google. Language learners expressed their comments about how far they have learned English, which part of the skills they emphasized and how these videos are helping or hindering their linguistic aptitude. In addition, all the linguistic and paralinguistic communications were taken into consideration while collecting data. Different data collection tools were used to collect the authentic data and make them reliable and validate.

7.5 Tools of Data Collection

7.5.1 Questionnaire

In order to collect the quantitative data, a sample close-ended questionnaire was prepared, different rating scale was given and asked to select one; both softcopy and hardcopy of the questionnaire were provided to the participants. Afterwards, one hundred and twenty copies of the filled-up questionnaire were collected to analyze the quantitative data. Microsoft Excel was used to analyze the quantitative data.

7.5.2 Observation

The naturalistic observation was conducted to collect the data for the descriptive part of the research. The observation tools were video characteristics, clarity, attractiveness, contents, skills, and teaching philosophy. Each aspect contains more than five questions, which were analyzed to acquire the observational information. On the other hand, the visit of the researchers to the offices of the YouTube channel owners and the conversation helped them to interpret the observation. Within one observation tool, several questions were made which provided the deep analysis of every aspect of the observation. At first, the researchers watched a class at a length and read all the comments related to the class. Then the observations were written

meticulously considering the observation points. As the researchers were also members of this community, it helped them a lot to understand, identify, and communicate with rest of the participants.

7.5.3 Interviews

The interview questions were asked to the teacher of ten respective channels and some of their interviews were recorded with their permission while some made candid request not to record. The interview questions cover information on their own academic qualification, their perception of language and language teaching, and their opinions and suggestion about the future of the YouTube language teaching. Besides, it also answers the replacement of the traditional tuition-oriented language teaching in Bangladesh by YouTube. Some questions were also related to the material adoption, content selection, content grading, using the language for instruction, feedback style etc. Teachers who came from other backgrounds like accounting or BBA but teach English were explained the registers related to English Language Teaching (ELT) before asking the questions.

7.5.4 Focus Group Discussion

In focus group discussion, ten participants were taken who watch YouTube videos and a group was formed on “Hangouts” a social communication site of Google where the researchers worked as a moderator. Before forming the group, the participants were explained their respective roles. In the group, we discussed so many issues related to YouTube language teaching and they expressed the advantages and disadvantages of watching YouTube language teaching videos. On the other hand, they mentioned about some shortcomings of the videos of some particular channels from their perspective. Though it was really difficult to conduct the discussion, it was continued for more than ten days maintaining regular intervals. All the open-ended questions were discussed here to clear the idea. In addition, every member of the group informed the researchers how these channels are helping them to learn English and how they are getting deprived of several issues like speaking skills, adequate input etc. At last, this group discussion gave a very intensive and explanatory opinion to interpret and analyze the data.

8. Data Presentation and Analysis

In this part, both qualitative and quantitative data are presented. The quantitative data are presented in terms of statistical measurement and represented in both pie and bar charts and the qualitative data are described in chronologically, first observation, then interviews and finally focus group discussion.

8.1 Questionnaire Data

A survey questionnaire was formed to know which is the most liked YouTube language teaching and learning channel in Bangladesh. The questionnaire was sent to one hundred and fifty participants, and one hundred and twenty responses were recorded. The data is represented in figure 2 showing 25% learners selected 10 Minutes School as the most favorite YouTube language teaching and learning channel though it covers other subjects along with English. In addition, this channel also has around 350 thousand subscribers and is verified by YouTube authority. 17% percent learners chose Saifur's Education for language teaching and learning. Besides, 12% percent learners selected Shafin's English Language Club as their preference. The rest 3% learners selected English Club BD and it was the lowest. The subscriber number of this channel was also comparatively less than the other channels. Therefore, the pie chart is depicting the most viewed and liked channels in Bangladesh.

8.2 Observation Data

8.2.1 Channel one

To begin with, this channel facilitates the education system making learning easy and stress-free in Bangladesh. Some IBA students created this channel to make learning easy and cost free. The channels started teaching English language especially for the competitive board exam in Bangladesh. This channel joined YouTube on August 11, 2015 and has acquired 21,108,725 views and 3,76,733 subscribers until now. At starting point, they used page and marker to explain any topic from grammar. The video quality of this channel is very good (720p to 1080p), the picture used to explain the topic is relevant, and culturally appropriate. The use of background music is relaxing and makes the students feel the positive vibe.

Figure 2: The Most Favorite YouTube Channels

However, few learners grumbled about the background music. Besides, all the tags of their videos are relevant to the video. Along with this, in the description box, the related links are given if further supports are needed to comprehend the topic. At the very beginning, the facilitators catch the attention of the learner with beautiful smile and enthusiastic attitude. Each video opens with a beep sound which pushes the learner to watch the whole video. The facilitator maintains proper paralinguistic behaviors like gesture, posture, eye contact etc. with the learners, which grab the attention of the learners. In terms of clarity, the class facilitator always looks prepared and use appropriate body language to deliver the information. Most of their videos stand alone and if any lesson depends on another video, they provide the lesson link on the description box. The facilitators always use L1 (Bengal) to explain the topic and no subtitle is used. Instead of using pens, rulers, and page as materials, they use smart board, animation etc. In addition, the pace of the video is appropriate for the students. In terms of comments, after watching the videos, learners post comments on the comment section. Any derogative and bad comment is deleted by the admin panel. Learners can also dislike their videos.

Figure 3: Language Used to Post Comments

Most contents were selected in relation to different big stake examinations like SSC, HSC, BCS etc. in addition, their content represents grammatical aspect of language. Lesson time is usually not more than five minutes but some of the videos that deal with IELTS topics exceed more than ten minutes. They deal with the syntax of the language, no emphasis is given on the other skills like speaking, reading, listening and writing. As they have come from non-linguistic and non-ELT background, they are not aware of the different teaching approach and methods.

To sum up, the repetition of difficult words, student's feelings (Affective Filter), use of L1 to explain topic and the feedback by comments are given to keep learners active and enthusiastic which motivate learners to achieve their goals and objectives.

8.2.2 Channel Two

This channel started to teach language on YouTube on May 17, 2015 and has 39,577 subscribers and 1,819,554 views. The owner of this channel is a renowned ex-professor from IBA who started coaching to teach English in Bangladesh before the inauguration of such YouTube channels. Besides online language teaching, it has an institution where they teach English to academicians and job seekers. Along with this, they publish different books related to language skills like grammar, vocabulary etc. In their video, they record the class with some students and then upload it on YouTube. Therefore,

the learners who are watching the video get the touch of a real class. The facilitators teach language by conducting a real class where interaction, teacher's active role, learners' role, feedback are present. The video quality is not up to the mark but enough to watch. All of their videos are more than ten minutes. The tag like "Saifur's sir 01...15" was very disturbing for the learners to guess what inside the video. The video starts with an opening sound and then the facilitators start with the topic without any greetings. Sometime the facilitators look very robotic and dull, but so proactive with the lesson. However, the instructor seems prepared with the lesson but he does not roam around the class while conducting. The facilitator use tangible materials like marker, board, books etc. The teacher used only response to the relevant comments only.

The lesson videos only deal with intermediate to advance level learners. The instructors use L1 to explain the rules of language and the teaching method here is also Grammar-Translation method with emphasis on the translation. In the classroom, the facilitators often use translation to demonstrate the rules of the target language. According to the learners, the most disturbing thing is the advertising of their books in the middle of the class and sudden appearance of the commercial ads of their address on the screen while taking the class. They follow chronological phases to take the class and the objective of the lesson is not stated clearly. In here, a teacher asks the in-class students about unknown words and drills the pronunciation so it is a chance for the online learners to practice and articulate the words with the students and after the students. Sometime in-class students ask about different problems about the lesson and the teacher gives feedback, which helps the online learners. They emphasize on syntax, vocabulary, and conduct classes using their own invented method called FM-method.

8.2.3 Channel Three

This channel started its journey on March 1, 2016 and has already achieved 2,590,238 views and 35,042 subscribers. It is little bit different compared to the previous two. It teaches the language in terms of functional point of view. They present high definition video and resolution is very clear. There is no fixed length for video, the length depends on the content and the topic of each lesson is given very precisely so that learners do not get confused. The facilitators have good eye contact with the learners and seem enthusiastic

which motivates the learners. The instructors seem well prepared and use appropriate body language to deliver the information. Compared to the previous two, it gives more emphasis on speaking and design each lesson in terms of daily life conversation, which learners listen to and take input. Facilitators use L2 and their pronunciation is native like. The facilitators use different role-play activities with the students, which the online learners watch, and learn the function of the language. The theoretical underlying of this channel is the notion-function syllabus and the interactional view of language. Besides, the facilitators arrange drama, enact it in English with the students, and provide subtitle for online learners and the play has a moral, which seems very fascinating. At the starting of the channel, the facilitators used whiteboard, marker, and duster as tangible materials. There is no commercial disturbance while a video is running. The exercises they use in the classroom are authentic and real life based so the online learners are getting familiar with the situational English. In this channel, learners are getting more comprehensive input which is important to learn a language as Stephen Krashen said. As the facilitators emphasize two skills in which one is receptive like listen and another is productive like speaking, they provide many interactive videos from where learners get input. Both L1 and L2 are used on the videos. Among his 96 YouTube language-learning videos, 71 are on functional point of view of language, 19 are from grammatical point of view, and rest of them are miscellaneous.

Figure 4: Types of Lesson Provided by YouTube Channels

So this channel is organized with a different philosophy of language teaching from where learners will be able to be fluent in English and will be able to use the functional English when they face real life situation.

8.2.4 Channel Four:

It started earlier on Dec 5, 2016 but could not achieve popularity. It has only 62,139 views and 12,844 subscribers and the channel has published only thirty-two videos on YouTube about language teaching. The most notable fact is that this channel is teaching language without any visible facilitator, this channel just provides the voice who reads the lesson on the screen. It has some videos on English grammar, sentence connectors and parts of speech. The quality of the video is not up to the mark and no background music is used. Most of their videos are about 10 minutes long; the tag of each video is given precisely. The interaction section in this channel by putting comments is also not very frequent. The invisible facilitator selects topic according to grammatical orientation of language. However, in the description box, some additional information and topic related links are given. It focuses only on syntax; other skills like speaking, listening etc. are not taken into consideration. As the lessons are grammar based, grammar is taught in deductive way. On the other side, the tone of the facilitator is very monotonous and the pitch level of the narrator is very robotic. The facilitator mostly uses L1 to teach the target language. The learners do not have the chance to feel the engagement to the class or the lesson. The grading of the content is randomly selected and presented but not properly maintained. The pace of the video and talking rate of the teacher are relatively fast.

8.2.5 Channel Five:

This channel is the strangest one that started so long ago in 2014 but did not get adequate number of audience. The video quality is not so good and no background music is used during the lesson. Facilitators conduct some classes and some are run without facilitators. On the other hand, their tags contain both Bangla and English language. The facilitators do not maintain proper eye contact and the videos do not contain any subtitle. The video length of the classes is usually more than two minutes. The facilitators do not provide feedback and the interaction through comments seems useless for the students. They use L1 to teach the target language and all the skills are not taught. However, this channel has insufficient videos, most are on teaching vocabulary. In addition, it also teaches English phonetics and pronunciation. In the description box, nothing is written which creates another problem for the learners to comprehend the lesson. There are very few comments on each video of this channel.

8.3 Interviews

The interview questions were set to know their philosophy about language teaching and the theoretical idea and motivation, which help these YouTube language teachers to make video. To answer the first question, six teachers said that now English is an international language. If someone wants to go for higher studies, he or she needs to know English, and to keep pace with international trades and economic system, learning English is indispensable. Therefore, they are just doing their duty by teaching English. In addition, they said as YouTube is the world's best free video sharing social site and due to easy accessibility they have chosen YouTube to share their lessons. The rest four-teachers focused on economic profit. All of them have firm believe about the effectiveness of YouTube language teaching and learning in Bangladesh. They are rationally optimistic to think that the technological advancement will reduce all the traditional methods, approach, design, procedure etc. On the other hand, in terms of qualification, they answered that teachers should have linguistic knowledge but it does not necessarily mean that a teacher has to be from English language or ELT background. The teacher who came from ELT background explained the question in an accurate way because they are familiar with the terms used in this area. As the user of YouTube is increasing day by day and YouTube is reaching the furthest corners of the country, one day it will reduce the cost of language teaching, they opined. With the advancement of the internet and technology, students from all over the country will be able to use YouTube language learning videos for their learning. It cannot replace the traditional tuition-oriented teaching but can be a great supplement for the current language teaching methods in Bangladesh. In addition, they added that YouTube language teaching in Bangladesh should be monitored by an approved authority appointed by the government. Otherwise, there will be chaos and many unprofessional and unskillful language teachers will start to teach, as it is open media for all. In terms of skills, they told that the YouTube language teaching should include all the four basic skills such as speaking, reading, listening, and writing of the language.

8.4 Focus Group Discussion

In this part of data collection, a non-bias and authentic situation was created where learners felt free to share about the problems and the benefits of

YouTube videos of different channels they had watched. First, they said that they do not need to call anyone to understand any aspect of the lessons. As many channels provide videos on the same topic, they can study in a comparative way. If one faces problem to comprehend any topic, he or she can post a comment stating the problem. In addition, they can go to the next channels. They told that these types of videos help them for a short time study before any exam. For the visual learners, such online learning helps the most. Students can see the same video repeatedly which helps them to learn the topics profoundly. They also said that some facilitators are very useful to reduce the fear and stress about learning a new language. They help learners to feel at ease by giving motivation and inspire learners to go ahead. They mentioned about some videos, which are unnecessarily lengthy, and make it impossible to hold the attention all the time. They strongly opposed to the slide related teaching without any visible facilitator. In addition, they also told that before going to study a topic from the course book, they search on YouTube to know the general knowledge of that topic. They also mentioned about the uploading time of the video and at a time, how many videos they should upload. After uploading one video, they need to provide at least two days and let all the students watch and give feedback on the comment and the facilitator should reply to all the related comments on the comments section. Whereas they told us that, except few channels the rest do not reply on the comments section. Sometime other students reply instead of the facilitators but they cannot be sure if the feedback is right or wrong. They also mentioned about any assigned work not given by the facilitator. Sometimes the examples provided by the facilitators are not authentic and culturally appropriate. They mentioned about the use of language as the medium of instruction. The learners prefer both L1 and L2 initially and as time goes, L2 should be used more. They also talked about the integrated language teaching approach and they should be provided with plenty of assignments which they will do after the lesson and submit it through e-mail to the facilitators and he will check and provide feedback for them. They also raised objection regarding the abusive comments in the comments box and demanded for an automatic software that will delete the bad comments.

9. Findings

This study deals with a very recent and emerging issue in Bangladesh. Some of the channels started later but came first in terms of viewers and subscribers

because of their content presentation, analytical ability of the topic, presentation skills, webpage design, simplicity etc. Now-a-days students are more dependable on YouTube for any inquiry compared to Google because it gives them a visual demonstration. On the other hand, native speakers started YouTube language teaching just after the inauguration of YouTube. In Bangladesh, YouTube language teaching started in 2014 but it is now increasing. Active and energetic teachers are coming to this field voluntarily. The research finds that the self-starting facilitators who are teaching language through YouTube are mostly from non-linguistic background. They did not have any education on language and training on language teaching. Among all the channels, YouTube authority authorizes only one channel and YouTube pays the channel producer for his videos. So, channels need to fulfill the conventions of YouTube to be verified. After talking with the teachers, it is evident that they conduct YouTube classes based on the target learners. They select contents by following traditional grammar books like 'Applied English Language Grammar' by P C Das that is written on structural view of language. On the other hand, they describe the item directly from those books. Their attitude towards learners is like a traditional teacher where learners are passive not active. In addition, learners spend 1 to 2 hours daily on YouTube who are consistently watching YouTube for language learning. It does not mean that they watch different videos from different channels but different videos from the same channels. Learners are seen attempting to utilize or incorporate the earned knowledge with real life.

Besides, the tag and the inside videos of some channels did not match for that reason learners face unwanted situation. Though many learners watch the videos, very few post comments about the lessons. Therefore, the majority of the learners face the fear and language related barrier to comment. There is no follow-up lesson for a lesson after receiving feedback from learners. Facilitators should arrange a follow-up class based on the problem and demand of the topic.

In terms of skills, not a single channel covers the four skills of English language. Most of them deal with syntax and vocabulary that demonstrates us the dominance of grammar in online language teaching. In addition, the way they teach word meaning is not pragmatically correct. Words should be taught in context not in an isolated way.

10. Conclusion

To sum up, the online language learners are increasing day by day as the access to the internet is easier now. Therefore, the online teachers should be more aware of selecting, sequencing, and teaching contents. Besides, within the one macro-community of Bangladeshi YouTube language learners, there are several micro-communities where their communication, attitudes, style of language learning, presentation of language and the philosophy of language are almost similar. Each of this micro-community needs to be explored through empirical study to figure out the current linguistic and paralinguistic behavior they are showing towards YouTube Language learning videos. The education ministry of Bangladesh should monitor or take control of potential English language teaching zones where learners will learn language in a natural way. The facilitators need to go under teacher-training projects to be more skillful in language teaching. One very important issue is to deal with the learners of different levels and socio-cultural background. Therefore, the channels should decorate their content according to the different level of learners and there has to be a scale to measure the level of learners like Common European Framework (CEF).

Before conducting any lesson, facilitators can arrange a poll to check the importance and acceptance of the topic to the learners. Otherwise, it will be redundant and monotonous to the learners. Teacher should be aware of the philosophy of the language and his own philosophy of language teaching while taking any class and keep it in mind for which level of the students he is making the language learning videos and what should be done and what should be avoided during the class. Therefore, to get the real scenario of the online language teaching in Bangladesh, more netnographic investigations should be conducted on different aspects of language teaching.

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Appendix

This survey is conducted by Al Mahmud Rumman and Sheikh Mobasher Ahmed to better understand the YouTube language, especially for English, teaching and learning scenario in Bangladesh. This questionnaire consists of four sections. This is not a test so there is no right or wrong answers. The researchers are interested in your personal opinion. Please read each instruction carefully and give your answers sincerely, as only this will guarantee the success of the investigation. Thank you very much for your help.

Part 1

Please provide the following information by ticking (✓) in the box or writing response in the space. All the fields marked with an asterisk (*) is mandatory.

Name: _____

Age*: _____ Nationality * _____

Gender *: Male Female Other

Occupation*: _____

Mobile number: _____

Why do you watch YouTube language learning videos?*

(Answer can be more than one option)

- Academic Purposes.
- Job Purposes.
- Business purposes
- Entertainment purposes
- Others

If any other purpose, please mention.

.....

.....

.....

.....

Part 2

In this part, we would like you to tell us how much you like or dislike with the following YouTube channels by simply bolding a number from 1 to 6. Please do not leave out any of items.

<i>Not at all</i>	<i>Not so much</i>	<i>So-so</i>	<i>A little</i>	<i>Quite a lot</i>	<i>Very much</i>
1	2	3	4	5	6

(Ex.) if you like 10 Minutes school very much, write this:

<i>10 Minutes School</i>	1	2	3	4	5	6
--------------------------	----------	---	---	---	---	---

<i>1. Saifur's Education</i>	1	2	3	4	5	6
<i>2. 10 Minutes School</i>	1	2	3	4	5	6
<i>3. Talent Hut Institute Bangla</i>	1	2	3	4	5	6
<i>4. Unique English World</i>	1	2	3	4	5	6
<i>5. Live school Bd</i>	1	2	3	4	5	6
<i>6. Bangla to English speaking course</i>	1	2	3	4	5	6
<i>7. Technical English learning home</i>	1	2	3	4	5	6
<i>8. Shafin's English language club</i>	1	2	3	4	5	6
<i>9. English club BD</i>	1	2	3	4	5	6
<i>10. Tutorial world 20</i>	1	2	3	4	5	6

If there is any other, please mention the name and why you like it.

.....

.....

.....

.....

Part 3

The complete guideline:

A- Video Characteristics:

- 1) What is the quality of the pictures? Low quality, high quality?
.....
- 2) What is the quality of the video? Low, medium, high quality?
.....
- 3) What is the quality of the audio such as the narration and the back ground music?
.....
- 4) When was the video uploaded?
.....
- 5) How long is the video?
.....
- 6) Does the video contain relevant tags?
.....
- 7) Is the video categorized in the right category i.e. language teaching?
.....

B- Attractiveness:

- 1) Do the first seconds or minutes of the video gain the YouTubers' attention?
.....
- 2) Does the facilitator have a good eye contact by looking at the camera?
.....
- 3) Does the video contain relevant music at the beginning or as back ground?
.....
- 4) Does the thumbnail of the video attract YouTubers?
.....
- 5) Does the facilitator show enthusiasm about the lesson video?
.....

C- Clarity:

- 1) Does the instructor seem to be prepared?

-
- 2) Does the instructor use good body language to deliver the information?
.....
- 3) Does the video depend on other videos? Or can it stand alone?
.....
- 4) Does the video contain subtitles or captions?
.....
- 5) Does the subtitle contain different colors?
.....
- 6) Does the teacher use other tangible materials such as pens, signs, rulers to teach?
.....
- 7) Is the pace fast, slow, medium?
.....

D- Reaction:

- 1) How do the YouTubers react through the comments?
.....
- 2) Does the teacher respond to the students' comments?
.....
- 3) Are any of the comments deleted?
.....
- 4) Are there any unrelated comments?
.....
- 5) How many people like the video?
.....
- 6) How many people dislike the video?
.....
- 7) How many times has the video been watched?
.....
- 8) How many YouTubers have chosen the video as one of their favourite videos?
.....
- 9) In which part of the world more people have watched the video?
.....
- 10) Is the video embedded on other websites?
.....
- 11) What age is the video popular with?
.....

-
12) What gender is the video popular with?
.....
- 13) How do people find the video?
.....
- 14) Does the video have honours from YouTube? Such as; most viewed, most favourite, highest rated?
.....

E- Content:

- 1) Does the teacher give an acceptable time for the YouTubers to answer their questions?
.....
- 2) Does the video contain several steps? Introduction, main stage, conclusion?
.....
- 3) Are the objectives of the video stated clearly?
.....
- 4) Does the video contain unrelated contents such as commercial ads and personal stories?
.....
- 5) Does the video contain culturally sensitive materials?
.....
- 6) Does the video contain authentic exercises and examples of language use?
.....
- 7) Does the title of the video reflect the content of the video? Or, on the contrary, does it mislead potential viewers?
.....
- 8) Does the teacher use examples to clarify points?
.....
- 9) Does the teacher repeat the important words, grammar points and questions?
.....
- 10) Does the teacher define difficult terms or words?
.....
- 11) Does the teacher summarize the video lesson?
.....

F- Skills:

- 1) Does the teacher emphasize on speaking?
.....
- 2) Does the teacher emphasize on listening?
.....
- 3) Does the teacher emphasize on writing?
.....
- 4) Does the teacher emphasize on reading?
.....
- 5) Is the teacher focusing on the syntax of that language?
.....
- 6) Is the teacher focusing on lexicons of that language?
.....
- 7) Is the teacher focusing all the skills in an integrated way?
.....

G - Teaching methodology:

- 1) What is the theory of the nature of language the teacher is following?
.....
- 2) What is the theory of the nature of language teaching the teacher is following?
.....
- 3) Is the teacher practicing any particular method to teach language?
.....
- 4) What is the nature of student – teacher interaction?
.....
- 5) How are the feeling of the students dealt with?
.....
- 6) Which language is the teacher using more? L1 or L2?
.....

Part 4**Interview questions:**

1. Why have you selected YouTube for language teaching?
2. What is your opinion about the effectiveness of YouTube language teaching and learning in Bangladesh?

3. What is your academic qualification to become an English language teacher? (skiable)
4. What philosophy of the nature of language and the nature of language teaching do you believe?
5. Do you think YouTube language teaching will reduce the cost of language teaching?
6. Do you think YouTube language teaching will replace the traditional tuition-oriented language teaching methods in Bangladesh?
7. Does the YouTube language teaching cover the four basic skills of language?
8. Please, explain your opinions and suggestions for the development of the YouTube language teaching.